

TECHNICAL REPORT

D1.1: Report 1 on actions to create interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Approved by	All project partners
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Abstract	This deliverable report provides the plan for the creation of ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups (education, gender, long-term implications, potential future returns). The Interdisciplinary Working Groups aim to bring together different partners/stakeholders from different disciplines in order to explore different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.
Keywords	Interdisciplinary; working; groups.

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Creation / Change	Page
1.0	10/02/2021	Document approved by all Partners	All

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1. (Coordinator)	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zürich	ETH	Switzerland
2.	University of Würzburg	UoW	Germany
3.	University of Barcelona	UoB	Spain
4.	University of Crete	UoC	Greece
5.	Stroke Alliance for Europe (SAFE)	SAFE	Pan-European
6.	Experian	EXP	Portugal
7.	Magnebotix	MGBX	Switzerland
8.	Discovery Foundation	DF	Greece
9.	Verhaert	VERT	Belgium

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable documents activities that are performed in Work Package (WP) 1 “Build-up an interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery in clinical environment regarding education, gender differences, long-term implications, and potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation”. The WP1 objectives include:

- Creating ANGIE’s Interdisciplinary Working Groups.
- Organising public debates.
- Targeting European and Local Governments.

The purpose of this document is to provide the plan for the creation of ANGIE’s Interdisciplinary Working Groups (education, gender, long-term implications, potential future returns). The Interdisciplinary Working Groups aim to bring together different partners/stakeholders from different disciplines in order to explore different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.

1.1. Scope

The present document is the Deliverable 1.1 “D1.1: Report 1 on actions to create interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery” (henceforth referred to as D1.1.) of the ANGIE project. The main objective of D1.1 is to provide the plan for creating ANGIE’s Interdisciplinary Working Groups. The ANGIE project aims to build-up an interdisciplinary community considering aspects of targeted drug delivery in clinical environments addressing:

- education
- gender differences
- long-term implications
- potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation

1.2. Audience

This document (D1.1) is available to the public and the European Commission.

2. INTERDISCIPLINARY WORKING GROUPS

The purpose of the creation of ANGIE’s Interdisciplinary Working Groups is to bring together stakeholders such as policy makers, the private sector, institutes, and civil society organisations to develop a new drug delivery technology, while promoting the public engagement, the ethical and legal discussions, as well as the relevant policy debates to foster its take-up by society.

The project partner responsible for the formation of the groups and the organisation of the meetings is Discovery Foundation (henceforth referred to as DF). The Dissemination and Innovation Manager had a meeting (via skype) with the Project Coordinator and the Technical Manager to discuss the following agenda:

1. Working group formation
2. Platform/application for membership registration
3. Roles and responsibilities
4. Meeting mechanics

The details and decisions taken concerning the individual points listed below can be found below.

2.1. Working Group Formation

The project partner DF sent invitations to all partners to participate in the groups and to nominate members for each group from within or outside their organisations. As soon as the working groups will be formatted, a public announcement will be posted to our meetup page and our website (soon to be uploaded) and will be circulated within organizations that are considered to have expertise in relation to the subject matter of the Working Group.

2.2. Membership platform/application

After thorough research, we identified 3 platforms (listed below) and came to the decision to proceed with meetup.com. We considered meetup.com to be the most effective platform to disseminate our project and attract memberships from different sectors. We have created our page entitled “Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group” where all meetups will take place, for each Working Group that soon will be formatted. Our page can be found at: <https://www.meetup.com/nanotechnology-for-targeted-drug-delivery-meetup-group/>

2.2.1. Meetup.com (<https://www.meetup.com/>)

Meetup.com is the most popular platform used to organize online groups that host in-person and virtual events for people with similar interests. Meetup has 49 million (approx.) members, and is available worldwide. Meetup features allow organisations to create multiple meetups, send invitations and track guest actions (confirmations or declines), and create branding with logos on social media pages. Organisations/companies can use Meetup for various purposes like improving outreach, planning and managing events, recruiting talent, initiating new deals, and learning about the market developments.

2.2.2. Eventbrite (<https://www.eventbrite.ca/>)

Eventbrite is a social platform used for hosting and registering for events. Eventbrite has 20 million (approx.) users and is available worldwide. Is a strictly online ticketing system and doesn't provide additional marketing tools.

2.2.3. Bylde (<https://www.bylde.com/>)

Bylde is a platform you can use to create, manage and grow your groups and communities. They have various groups across multiple industries like design, fashion, beauty, music, food, social and travel.

3. ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES

3.1. Work Package Leader

The project partner DF acting as the Work Package will be responsible for:

- Collect expressions of interest to participate in a Working group (nominations or self-nominations)
- Appoint a Chair for each Working group
- Update the meetup page with news and upcoming events
- Organising and coordinate the meetups with the Chair of each Working Group.
- Take notes and record the Working groups activities.

DF has appointed the Dissemination and Innovation Manager to serve as a Liaison to the Working Groups. His role consists of reporting to the Coordinator on the progress of the Working Groups and assisting the Chair of each Working Group with his knowledge and expertise.

3.2. Chair

The Chair of each Working Group will be responsible for:

- Develop and share an agenda for the meeting at least 7 calendar days in advance of the meeting
- Publicize in advance the time and the location of the Working Group meeting

3.3. Members

Each Working Group member will be expected to:

- Participate and contribute ideas and knowledge to working group discussions
- Bring concerns to other members or facilitators

4. MEETING METHODOLOGY

The overall aim is for the Working Groups is to run as “small-scale individual COST Actions”. Each group will meet at least twice a year and the meetings minutes will be reported to the Commission Services. The time and location of all Working group meetings will be publicized in advance. The Working Groups may choose to invite guest speakers with special knowledge and expertise to attend meetings to provide information and/or advice.

Meetings will be used for the presentation of work in progress, for the discussions of texts (e.g. potential manuscripts for publication), or to address a common issue. The focus of the working group will be exploring different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments and producing strategies and activities that eventually will address the respective issue or problem.